

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AXITINIB
IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM BY UV-
SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD**¹Santhosh Illendula, ¹A.Navya Sree, ¹CH.Ganesh, ¹K.Sneha, ¹M.Sravya, ¹B.Sayujya,
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Article Received: January 2019

Accepted: February 2019

Published: March 2019

Abstract:

A new simple, accurate, rapid, precise, reproducible and cost effective spectrophotometric method for the quantitative estimation of Axitinib in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. The developed visible spectrophotometric method for the quantitative estimation of Axitinib is based on measurement of absorption at maximum wavelength 253 nm using DMF with Water as a solvent. The stock solution of Axitinib was prepared, and subsequent suitable dilution was prepared in distilled water to obtain standard curve. The standard solution of Axitinib shows absorption maxima at 253 nm. The drug obeyed Beer Lambert's law in the concentration range of 5 - 25 µg/ml with regression 0.999 at 253 nm. The overall % recovery was found to be 99.6% which reflects that the method was free from the interference of the impurities and other excipients used in the bulk and marketed dosage form. The low value of % RSD was indicative of accuracy and reproducibility of the method. The % RSD for inter-day and intra-day precision was found to be 0.0326 and 0.0415 respectively which is <2% hence proved that method is precise. The results of analysis have been validated as per International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The developed method can be adopted in routine analysis of Axitinib in bulk and tablet dosage form.

Keywords: Axitinib, UV Visible Spectrophotometry, Method development, Validation, ICH guidelines, DMF, Accuracy, Precision.

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Please cite this article in press Santhosh Illendula et al., *Method Development and Validation of Axitinib in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form by Uv-Spectroscopic Method.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(03).

INTRODUCTION:

Axitinib N-methyl-2-((3-((E)-2-(pyridin-2-yl)ethenyl)-1H-indazol-6-yl)sulfanyl)benzamide; Inlyta; Pfizer, Pharmaceuticals, Inc; Figure 6) Axitinib is a benzamide and indazole derivative is used to treat renal cell carcinoma after failure of prior treatment with sunitinib or a cytokine and taken 5mg dose twice daily. It is an oral tyrosine kinase inhibitor and inhibits vascular endothelial growth factor VEGFR-1, VEGFR-2, and VEGFR-3 & platelet-derived growth factor receptor (PDGF) leading to blockade of signaling through this angiogenic pathway. In phase II

studies, axitinib showed single-agent activity in a variety of tumor types, including non-small cell lung cancer, advanced renal cell carcinoma and thyroid cancer. Axitinib effectively inhibits a mutated gene (BCR-ABL1[T315I]) that is common in chronic myeloid leukemias and adult acute lymphoblastic leukemias which have become resistant to other tyrosine kinase inhibitors like imatinib. It was approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration after showing a modest increase in progression-free survival, though there have been reports of fatal adverse effects.

Fig-1 Structure of Axitinib

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents: Methanol, Ethanol, Acetone, Dimethylsulphoxide, Sodium citrate with water.

Instruments:

The Spectroscopic analysis was carried out using Double beam PG Instruments recording UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU UV-1601) with 1mm path length matched quartz cells was used for analytical purpose.

REAGENTS AND SOLUTIONS:

Diluent preparation : In a 100ml volumetric flask take 50ml dimethyl formamide and make the volume up to the mark.

Preparation of Standard Solutions

Accurately weighed 100mg of Axitinib was weighed accurately and transferred into 100ml volumetric flask. About 10 ml of diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve. The volume was made up to the mark with same solvent. The final solution contained about 100µg/ml of axitinib. Working standard solution of Axitinib containing 10µg/ml for method. Finally add those above solutions and prepare the final solution is about 10µg/ml.

Preparation of Sample Solutions .

Take 20 Tablets average weight and crush in a mortar by using pestle and weight powder 100 mg equivalent weight of Axitinib sample into a 100ml clean dry volumetric flask, dissolve and make up to volume with diluent. Further dilution was done by transferring 0.1 ml of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with diluent.

Determination of wavelength of maximum absorbance for Axitinib

The absorbance of the final solution scanned in the UV spectrum in the range of 200 to 400nm against solvent mixture as blank.

Optimization of selection of Solvent

It is well known that the solvents do exert a profound effect on the quality and the shape of the peak. The choices of solvents for UV method development are: Methanol, Ethanol, DMF Acetonitrile, Dimethyl Sulphoxide, Sodium citrate etc. First optimize the different solvents. From that solvents DMF satisfied the all the optimized conditions.

Wavelength Selection

The standard solutions are prepared by transferring the standard drug in a selected solvent or mobile phase and finally diluting with the same solvent or diluent. That prepared solution is scanned in the visible wavelength

range of 200-400nm. This has been performed to know the maxima of Axitinib. While scanning the Axitinib solution we observed the maxima at 253 nm. The visible spectrum has been recorded on (SHIMADZU UV-1601 make UV – Vis spectrophotometer model UV-1601. The scanned visible spectrum is attached in the following page. The λ_{max} of the Axitinib was found to be 253 nm in diluents as solvent system..

METHOD VALIDATION:

Accuracy: Recovery study: To determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by adding different amounts (80%, 100%, and 120%) of pure drug of Axitinib were taken and added to the pre-analyzed formulation of concentration 10 μ g/ml. From that percentage recovery values were calculated. The results were shown in Table-1.

Precision:

Repeatability

The precision of each method was ascertained separately from the peak areas & retention times obtained by actual determination of six replicates of a fixed amount of drug. Axitinib (API) the percent relative standard deviations were calculated for Axitinib is presented in the Table-2.

Intermediate Precision:

Intra-assay & inter-assay:

The intra & inter day variation of the method was carried out & the high values of mean assay & low values of standard deviation & % RSD (% RSD < 2%) within a day & day to day variations for Axitinib revealed that the proposed method is precise. The results were shown in Table-3.

LINEARITY & RANGE:

The calibration curve showed good linearity in the range of 5-25 μ g/ml, for Axitinib (API) with correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.999 (Fig-2). A typical calibration curve has the regression equation of $y = 0.05965x + 0.010$ for Axitinib.

Standard solutions of Axitinib in the concentration range of 5 μ g/ml to 25 μ g/ml were obtained by transferring (5, 10, 15 and 20, 25 ml) of Axitinib stock solution (100ppm) to the series of clean & dry 10 ml volumetric flasks. The volumes in each volumetric flask were made up with the solvent system and mixed.

The data are shown in Table-6.

$$\text{Amount Present} = \frac{\text{Sample Absorbance}}{\text{Standard Absorbance}} \times \frac{\text{Standard Dilution}}{\text{Sample Dilution}} \times \frac{\text{Potency}}{100} \times \text{Average weight}$$

The absorbances of the solutions were measured at 253 nm against the solvent system as blank and calibration curve is plotted. The Lambert-Beer's Law is linear in concentration range of 5 to 25 μ g/ml at 253 nm for Axitinib. The results were shown in Table-4.

METHOD ROBUSTNESS:

Robustness of the method was determined by carrying out the analysis under different Wavelength i.e. at 251nm, 253nm and 255nm.. The respective absorbances of 10 μ g/ml were noted (SD < 2%) the developed UV-Spectroscopic method for the analysis of Axitinib (API). The results were shown in Table-5.

LOD & LOQ:

The LOD and LOQ were calculated by the use of the equations $\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / S$ and $\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S$ where σ is the standard deviation of intercept of Calibration plot and S is the average of the slope of the corresponding Calibration plot.

The Minimum concentration level at which the analyte can be reliably detected (LOD) & quantified (LOQ) were found to be 0.002148 & 0.326 μ g/ml respectively.

ASSAY OF AXITINIB IN DOSAGE FORM:

AXITINIB 5mg

Assay of marketed tablet formulation Brands :

Axitinib was procured from the local market as tablets of strength having 5mg, marketed with brand names of Inlyta. when referring to the generic drug name axitinib. These marketed formulations were manufactured by the .Pfizer Pharmaceuticals, respectively.

Weighed accurately about twenty tablets and calculate the weights of individual tablets and finally calculate the average weight. They were triturated to fine powder by using a mortar and pestle. The powdered tablet equivalent to 5mg of Axitinib was dissolved in 15ml of diluent with the help of sonication process and the final volume was made up to the mark with the diluent in 25 ml volumetric flask. The resulted solution was filtered using whatman filter paper (0.45 μ m). This final solution was further diluted to obtain 10 μ g/ml concentration of the solution by using diluents used as a solvent and observed by UV analysis. This procedure was repeated in triplicate.

$$\% \text{Content} = \frac{\text{Amount Present}}{\text{Label Claim}} \times 100.$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The standard solutions of Axitinib in Sodium citrate with Water (10 µg/ml) subjected to a scan individually at the series of wavelengths of 400 nm to 800 nm. Absorption maximum of Axitinib was found to be at 253 nm. Therefore, 253 nm was selected as λ_{max} of Axitinib for the present study. The calibration curve of Axitinib was found to be linear in the range of 5-25 µg/ml at 253 nm. Therefore, it was clear that Axitinib can be determined without interference of any irrelevant substance in single component pharmaceutical products. The used technique was initially attempted on bulk drugs in their synthetic sample and concentrations were estimated.

The % recovery was carried out at 3 levels, 80%, 100% and 120% of Axitinib standard concentration. Three samples were prepared for each recovery level. The solutions were then analyzed, and the percentage recoveries were found to be satisfactory within the acceptable limits as per the content of the label claim for marketed tablet dosage form. The newly developed method was validated according to the ICH guidelines and the method validation parameters.

The developed method was subjected to do the various method validation parameters such as specificity, accuracy, precision, linearity and range, limit of detection and limit of quantification, robustness and ruggedness etc.

Fig-2: Calibration curve of Axitinib (API).

Table-1: Results of accuracy :

Level of Recovery	Sample Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
80%	8	0.4938	99.9	99.91
80%	8	0.4889	98.9	
80%	8	0.4911	99.3	
100%	10	0.6172	99.7	98.4
100%	10	0.6093	98.4	
100%	10	0.6134	99.1	
120%	12	0.7423	99.8	99.65
120%	12	0.7394	99.5	
120%	12	0.7404	99.6	

Acceptance criteria: correlation coefficient should not be less than 0.990.

PRECISION:

Repeatability: Table-2: Results of Repeatability

S.No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance
1	10	253	0.6180
2	10	253	0.6107
3	10	253	0.6113
4	10	253	0.6172
5	10	253	0.6099
6	10	253	0.6109
Mean \pm S.D.			0.613
Standard Deviation			0.003601
% RSD			0.587

Table-3: Results of intra-Day & inter-Day

Con. taken ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Observed Conc. Of Axitinib ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) by the proposed method			
	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Absorbance	Statistical Analysis	Con. found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Statistical Analysis
10	0.6132	Mean = 1.43	0.6120	Mean = 0.612
10	0.6128	SD = 0.000208	0.6118	SD = 0.0002
10	0.6129	%RSD = 0.0415	0.6122	%RSD = 0.0326

Table-4: Results of Linearity

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (n=6)
5	0.3041
10	0.6098
15	0.9102
20	1.2013
25	1.4998

Acceptance criteria: correlation coefficient should not be less than 0.9990

Table-5: Result of Method Robustness Test

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Wavelength	Absorbance	Statistical Analysis
10	251	0.6312	Mean = 0.6242 SD = 0.009168 % RSD = 1.46876
10		0.6298	
10		0.6301	
10	253	0.6114	
10		0.6119	
10		0.6128	
10	255	0.6301	
10		0.6299	
10		0.6309	

Table-6: Assay Results of Marketed Formulations

Formulations	Actual concentration of Axitinib [Label Claim] ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount obtained of Axitinib ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Axitinib
Inlyta	5	4.97	99.4

CONCLUSION:

From the experimental studies it can be concluded that best UV-Spectroscopic method is developed for Axitinib in bulk and marketed pharmaceutical dosage form. The developed method for the drug (Axitinib) was found to be accurate and precise.

The great features of spectrophotometric methods are their simplicity, economical and rapidity. The results of method validation showing that the developed analytical procedure is suitable for its intended purpose and meets the Guidelines given by the ICH.

The developed method was successfully applied for the routine analysis of Axitinib in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form in the future.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors are grateful to the management of Nalanda College of Pharmacy, Nalgonda for providing the facilities to carry out the present research work

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